

Supplementary material to manuscript:

Identifying and characterizing social media communities: a socio-semantic network approach

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Journal	Citations
<i>Qualitative Health Research</i>	169
<i>BMJ Open</i>	29
<i>International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health</i>	13
<i>International Journal of Qualitative Methods</i>	12
<i>PloS One</i>	12
<i>BMC Public Health</i>	11
<i>Nursing Inquiry</i>	11
<i>Social Science & Medicine</i>	11
<i>Journal of Clinical Nursing</i>	9
<i>Qualitative Report</i>	9
<i>BMC Health Services Research</i>	8
<i>Journal of Advanced Nursing</i>	7
<i>Frontiers in Psychology</i>	6
<i>International Journal of Indigenous Health</i>	5
<i>Sociology of Health & Illness</i>	5
<i>American Journal of Hospice & Palliative Medicine</i>	4
<i>BMC Medical Ethics</i>	4
<i>European Journal of Oncology Nursing</i>	4
<i>Frontiers in Psychiatry</i>	4
<i>Gerodontology</i>	4
<i>Health & Social Care in the Community</i>	4
<i>International Journal of Qualitative Studies on Health And Well-being</i>	4
<i>International Journal of Social Research Methodology</i>	4
<i>Journal of Aggression Maltreatment & Trauma</i>	4
<i>Journal of Human Lactation</i>	4
<i>Journal of Medical Internet Research</i>	4
<i>Medical Education</i>	4
<i>Midwifery</i>	4
<i>Nursing Ethics</i>	4
<i>Nursing Open</i>	4

